

TIME MANAGEMENT SKILL AND TECHNIQUES

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" Don't say don't have enough time, you have exactly the sam number of hours per day those were given to Helen Keler, Pasteur Mother Teresa, Leonardo da vinci and Albert Einstein."

- H.Jackson Brow

1. Introduction

Time management in personal life is a discipline that everyone] acknowledges is worthwhile while simultaneously ignoring it. There! seems to be something in the human spirit that rebels against time management, despite realizing in benefits. It's rather like eating the! right food - we can acknowledge all the benefits of eating lots of fruit and vegetables, we can even enjoy eating fruits and vegetables- and still pig out on junk food.

Thus, ability to ignore time management is very sad. There are! plenty of variations on the theme of 'so much to do so little time to do in it'. Few of us have time to get everything we really want to dpi complete. Few of us manage to efficiently balance, work and home life, business and pleasure, stress and stress relief. Good time! management is more than a nit-picking discipline that will appeal to those who like everything in its place, it is a vehicle for getting morel done and having a better life. If only it can be made practical.

If we want to improve our time management skills or overall personal effectiveness, one has to follow some guidelines which will help us to manage the time fruitfully. This personal time management guide is dedicated to building a stronger foundation! for our success.

This paper makes time management practical by using some skills! and abilities i.e. to set priorities and manage the time to achieve! goals, to organize efficiently daily actions, makes smarter decisions! faster, to work in a team and to prevent burnout.

Time Management

Time Management refers to the way that you organize and plan; how long you spend time on specific activities

Time management is the act or process of planning and exercising conscious control over the amount of time spend on specific activities, especially to increase effectiveness, efficiency and productivity.

We ever wondered how it is that same people seem to have enough time to do everything that they want to, whereas others are always rushing from task to task and never seem to finish anything.

Is it just that the former have less to do? No, it's much more likely that they are using their time more effectively and practicing good time management skills.

It seems that there is no enough time in the day. But all have we 24 hours, then why it is that some people achieve so much more with their time than others? The answer lies in good time management through some skills and guidelines.

Time management is not very difficult as a concept, but it's surprisingly hard to do in practice. It requires the investment of a little time upfront to priorities and to organize yourself but once done, you will find that with minor tweaks, your day and indeed your week and month, fall into place in an orderly fashion, with time for everything you need to do

To building a stronger foundation for your success following are your skills and abilities

- set priorities and **manage your time** to meet deadlines,
- set and achieve **goals**,
- effectively organize your **daily actions**,
- make **smarter decisions** faster,
- uncover **better options**,
- work in a **team** or build one,

- prevent **burnout**

3. Manage your Time i.e. Time management skills and techniques

Time management skills are your abilities to recognize and solve personal time management problems. The goal of these time management lessons is to show you what you can do to improve those skills. With good time management skills you are in control of your time and your life, of your stress and energy levels. You make progress at work. You are able to maintain balance between your work, personal, and family lives. You have enough flexibility to respond to surprises or new opportunities.

All time management skills are learnable. More than likely you will see much improvement from simply becoming aware of the essence and causes of common personal time management problems. With these time management lessons, you can see better which time management techniques are most relevant for your situation.

Just get started with them. Many of your problems gradually disappear. If you already know how you should be managing your time, but you still don't do it, don't give up. What you may be overlooking is the psychological side of your time management skills, psychological obstacles hidden behind your personality.

Depending on your personal situation, such obstacles may be the primary reason why you procrastinate, have difficulties saying no, delegating, or making time management decisions.

The psychological component of your time management skills can also be dealt with. The time management skills information below will point at a relevant solution for your situation.

Ideas, tips, tools and more to help you for organize your home, your office and your life!

Ability to beat procrastination and laziness is among the most important time management skills to learn. Identify your causes of procrastination and start fighting it now.

Good decision making skill is the foundation for life and time management skills.

Prioritizing skills allow you to focus on what is most important. Learn to set priorities wisely, and you will achieve more and will have more of personal or family time.

Planning is an important time management technique. Planning optimizes your efforts of achieving a goal. Learn to plan efficiently. Simple and powerful techniques to convert your goals and ideas into an effective action plan.

Why delegation skill is important for personal time management? how to choose delegate? how to delegate. How to train your delegation skill ? these are the questions before us.

Well-developed coping skills help you maintain control and do the best that could be done when faced with outstanding challenges. Time log is a very effective time management learning tool. Your minimal effort and a few tips and techniques can eliminate much of wasted time and help you reach balance.

4. Personal goal setting

Why is personal goal setting so important in personal time management? From the time management perspective, your life is a sequence of big and small choices and decisions. It is those choices that you really manage.

Personal goal setting is the wisdom that comes out of a lot of practical experience and psychology research to help you direct your conscious and subconscious decisions towards success, building up your motivation to achieve your personal or business goals. Plan your work, work your plan towneted do list is a simple technique that can increase your productivity by 20 percent or more, if you don't use it already. It also has extra benefits of clearing your mind and saving you energy and stress.

Try to spend 5-10 minutes each day on planning your activities with a daily to do list. Start your day with it. Even better, every evening write a plan for the next day, listing your daily things to do. It is important that you actually writing your tasks.

Some people are more comfortable doing it on paper, while others prefer using a computer. Try and see what works better for you.

After you've listed all your tasks, review your to do list and decide on the priority of each task. Give higher priority to the tasks that get you closer to your goals.

A proven simple technique is an ABC rating of your priorities. Mark the tasks on your to do list with "A's" if they are critical for your goals and simply must be done that day (or else you face serious consequences). "B's" are less urgent but still important tasks that you should start right after you are done with "As". "C's" are "nice to do" things that you could do if you have any time left after "A's" and "B's". Those tasks can be safely moved to another day.

One important tip to keep in mind is if during a day some new unplanned task comes up, don't do anything until you put that new task on your list and rate it by priority. See it written among the other tasks and put it in perspective. The more you let go off the urge to skip that simple step, the more productive and satisfied you become. When making to do list, break down your complex tasks into smaller manageable pieces, and focus on one at a time.

Finally, after completion of a task take a moment to look at the result and feel the satisfaction of the progress.

3. Decision making skills and techniques

We use our decision making skills to solve problems by selecting one course of action from several possible alternatives. Decision making skills are also a key component of time management skills.

Decision making can be hard. Almost any decision involves some conflicts or dissatisfaction. The difficult part is to pick one solution where the positive outcome can outweigh possible losses. Avoiding decisions often seems easier. Yet, making your own decisions and accepting the consequences is the only way to stay in control of your time, your success, and your life. If you want to learn more on how to make a decision, here are some decision making tips to get you started.

A significant part of decision making skills is in knowing and practicing good decision making techniques. One of the most practical decision making techniques can be summarized in those simple decision making steps:

1. **Identify the purpose of your decision.** What is exactly the problem to be solved? Why it should be solved?
2. **Gather information.** What factors does the problem involve?
3. **Identify the principles to judge the alternatives.** What standards and judgement criteria should the solution meet?
4. **Brainstorm and list different possible choices.** Generate ideas for possible solutions.
5. **Evaluate each choice in terms of its consequences.** Use your standards and judgement criteria to determine the and cons pros of each alternative.
6. **Determine the best alternative.** This is much easier after you go through the above preparation steps.
7. **Put the decision into action-** Transform your decision into specific plan of action steps. Execute your plan.
8. **Evaluate the outcome of your decision and action steps.** This is an important step for further development of your decision making skills and judgment.

Final remark - In everyday life we often have to make decisions fast, without enough time to systematically go through the above action and thinking steps. In such situations the most effective decision making strategy is to keep an eye on your goals and then let your intuition suggest you the right choice.

4. Brainstorming tips for better time management

The major bottleneck in any planning or problem solving process is brainstorming or generating new ideas and options for specific actions and solutions.

The resulting outcome of your solution or plan is only as good as your best options and ideas you put in it. It is also important how fast you can come up with new ideas, as you will need many of them in your time management and decision making.

Fortunately, there are ways to significantly improve your effectiveness in brainstorming new ideas.

Though sometimes word brainstorming refers to group brainstorming sessions, here we will look at how you can brainstorm to generate ideas on your own.

With very few exceptions, **everyone already has a natural ability of creative thinking.** Yet, that creative ability is fragile. It is easy to block it just by the way you use it, by your attitudes, by the way you think.

Here is a selection of brainstorming tips that can help you to unlock your idea generation ability. Those tips are like brainstorming tools that you can use systematically every time you need new ideas.

The best practical way to have good ideas is to **have many of them first**, and then to select the best ones. Generating many ideas fast is what brainstorming is focused on.

In your brainstorming session you can follow these steps.

First, take a few minutes to think about what it is you would ideally like to accomplish. How clear a picture you see in your mind? Try to refresh and extend your view of the problem. In particular, think of 5 people you know that come from different background than yours. Imagine what each of those people, one by one, would see in your problem, how they would approach it.

Now it is time to start the actual brainstorming exercise. Take a sheet of paper, a pen, and your watch. Set a goal to write a certain large number of options (over 10 or 20) or ideas within a specific short time interval (minutes). A good example is a goal to write 20 ideas within 5 minutes.

What is important in this activity is that you **focus on quantity** of ideas, not quality. When you brainstorm, you just write in a list manner whatever comes into your mind, and write fast. You let your imagination flow, you play. **Forget all judging or analyzing, common sense, rules, or practicality.**

A pressing, almost unrealistic, deadline plays an important role in the brainstorming session. It mobilizes your subconscious and conscious minds. It helps to paralyze your judgment, analysis, and other mental blocks, freeing your imagination.

After the time is up, take a few more minutes to brainstorm a few more ideas, until you feel you cannot squeeze anything more out of your mind. Often those last ideas will be the most valuable ones.

At the end of this brainstorming exercise you have a long list of ideas, options, and thoughts. You will discard most of them later, at the judgment stage. Yet, the ideas you eventually select tend to be much better than something that would logically follow from what you had in your mind before the brainstorming exercise.

The outcome may surprise you. It is worth every minute you spend on it.

5. Team work and team building essentials

Team building skills are critical for your effectiveness as a manager or entrepreneur. And even if you are not in a management or leadership role yet, better understanding of team work can make you are more effective employee and give you an extra edge in your corporate office.

A team building success is when your team can accomplish something much bigger and work more effectively than a group of the same individuals working on their own. You have a strong energy of individual contributions. But there are two critical factors in building a high performance team.

The first factor in team effectiveness is the diversity of skills and personalities. When people use their strengths in full, but can compensate for each other's weaknesses. When different personality types balance and complement each other.

The other critical element of team work success is that all the team efforts are directed towards the same clear goals, the team goals. This relies heavily on good communication in the team and the harmony in member relationships.

In real life, team work success rarely happens by itself, without focused team building efforts and activities. There is simply too much space for problems. For example, different personalities, instead of complementing and balancing each other, may build up conflicts. Or even worse, some people with similar personalities may start fighting for authority and dominance in certain areas of expertise. Even if the team goals are clear and accepted by everyone, there may be no team commitment to the group goals or no consensus on the means of achieving those goals: individuals in the team just follow their personal opinions and move in conflicting directions. There may be a lack of trust and openness that blocks the critical communication

and leads to loss of coordination in the individual efforts and on and on. This is why every team needs a good leader who is able to deal with all such team work issues.

Here are some additional team building ideas, techniques, and tips you can try when managing teams in your situation.

Make sure that the team goals are totally clear and completely understood and accepted by each team member.

Make sure there is complete clarity in who is responsible for what and avoid overlapping authority. For example, if there is a risk that two team members will be competing for control in certain area, try to divide that area into two distinct parts and give each more complete control in one of those parts, according to those individual's strengths and personal inclinations.

Build trust with your team members by spending one-on-one time in an atmosphere of honesty and openness. Be loyal to your employees, if you expect the same.

Allow your office team members build trust and openness between each other in team building activities and events. Give them some opportunities of extra social time with each other in an atmosphere that encourages open communication. Though be careful with those corporate team building activities or events in which socializing competes too much with someone's family time.

For issues that rely heavily on the team consensus and commitment, try to involve the whole team in the decision making process. For example, via group goal setting or group sessions with collective discussions of possible decision options or solution ideas. What you want to achieve here is that each team member feels his or her ownership in the final decision, solution, or idea. And the more he or she feels this way, the more likely he or she is to agree with and commit to the decided line of action, the more you build team commitment to the goals and decisions.

When managing teams, make sure there are no blocked lines of communications and you and your people are kept fully informed. Even when your team is spread over different locations, you can still maintain effective team communication. Just do your meetings online and slash your travel costs.

Be careful with interpersonal issues. Recognize them early and deal with them in full.

Don't miss opportunities to empower your employees. Say thank you or show appreciation of an individual team player's work.

Don't limit yourself to negative feedback. Be fair. Whenever there is an opportunity, give positive feedback as well.

Finally, though team work and team building can offer many challenges, the pay off from a high performance team is well worth it.

6. Eliminate procrastination

The essence of procrastination is very well reflected in this quote by Bernard Meltzer: "Hard work is often the easy work you did not do at the proper time."

Are you affected?

Have you ever seen your most important tasks being put off until later and then later and later, while you are getting busy with many not so important activities? Did you hope that you may have more time and better mood in the future to start the task and do it properly? Does an approaching deadline mean a crisis for you? Do you keep hesitating every time you make a decision?

" If you often see yourself in such low productivity situations, then there is a big chance that your life got under control of the procrastination habit. And those situations are only the most explicit symptoms.

What is it?

A basic definition of procrastination is putting off the things that you should be doing now. This happens with all of us time after time, g. Yet, what makes a big difference for your success is your ability to recognize procrastination reasons and expressions in their different forms, and to promptly take them under control, before this bad habit steals your opportunities, damages your career and pride, or destroys your relationships. So why do not you do it now?

Causes of procrastination

What are typical reasons why you procrastinate?

Here are a few of the most common situations to consider in your anti procrastination efforts.

It can be as simple as

Waiting for the right mood

Waiting for the right time

Then look at the way you organize your work. You may notice other reasons for procrastination like

Lack of clear goal

Underestimating the difficulty of the tasks

Underestimating the time required to complete the tasks

Unclear standards for the task outcomes

Feeling as the tasks are imposed on you from outside

Too ambiguous tasks

And there are also many connections with

Underdeveloped decision making skills

Fear of failure or fear of success

Perfectionism

7. Conclusion

From the above guidelines to manage our personal time, we ruminate in our mind that we always made time management of our goals but due to lack of techniques and skills of time management we spend too much time on certain goals, which can be achieved within very less time after following the proper techniques and skills of time management.

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